

RESEARCH ON THE ATTITUDES OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS FOR MATHEMATICS EDUCATION LESSONS

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the attitudes of the students of Primary School Teaching Department towards mathematics education lessons and to investigate whether it has effects in terms of different variables. Attitude Scale towards Mathematics Education lessons, developed by Türker and Turanlı (2008), was used to determine the attitude levels of primary school students in mathematics education lessons. In the analysis of the data, descriptive statistics, t-test parametric variable data and Kruskal Wallis statistics for non-parametric distributed parent status were used. As a result of the study, it was found that the students' attitudes in the Department of Primary Education Teaching towards mathematics education lessons were 3.40-4.20. We can say students' attitudes towards mathematics education lessons were at a good level. There was no significant effect on the attitudes of the students towards mathematics education courses in the first and fourth grade. According to the variables of father-mother education level, literate father-mother children had the highest level of attitudes and the father-mother children

with higher education had the lowest level of attitudes and mentioned differences were not statistically significant.

Keywords: Primary School Teaching, mathematics education, attitude.

1. Introduction

Mathematics is a tool that helps individuals discover their talents and think logically (Bulut, 1994). Meaningful mathematics education is performed by teachers, students and a learning environment. However, the role of teachers cannot be ignored. A teacher with a negative personality traits affects a child's thinking and course of their success (Erden, 1998). Not only personal characteristics, but also professional qualifications, knowledge in the subject matter, and knowledge in the field of teaching are required. The effects of teachers' skills and attitudes towards mathematics and lecturing are inevitable. In Turkey, the information that the teachers should have is given as "field knowledge", "knowledge of the teaching profession" and "general culture knowledge"; (Erden, 1998) are also elements to be recognized. In the following years, "field teaching knowledge" was added and the importance of this knowledge in teacher training programs was emphasized (Nakiboğlu and Karakoç, 2005). Shulman's (1986) model of PAB is the field knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical knowledge that the teacher should have. Koehler, Mishra & Yahya, (2007) emphasized that another model, the technological pedagogical field knowledge model, which is located at the center of the field, includes the relationships between them. This knowledge is not enough to have skills and competences. The transfer of knowledge is of great importance. As long as a teacher can tell what they know, they will have successfully used their field knowledge. Baki (2010) defines teaching knowledge

is in the form of knowing how the teacher will teach in the field together with the acquisitions of the curriculum, preparing appropriate materials, designing the appropriate educational environment, and recognizing the students depending on their cognitive, sensory development. Erden (1998) emphasizes the importance of the teacher's ability to teach. Mathematics Teaching in the Faculties of Education, Special Teaching Methods, Instructional Technologies and Material Development, School Experience I-II and Teaching Practice are counted among the lessons given within the scope of the teaching knowledge, and these lessons are aimed to gain the necessary skills for field teaching.

When the relevant field literature is examined, it is seen that there are few studies investigating attitudes towards application of education lessons. Türnüklü (2005), in his study on prospective mathematics teachers, concluded that having mathematical knowledge is necessary to realize mathematical pedagogical field knowledge. In their study, Özgen and Obay (2016) concluded that the mean scores of pre-service teachers' attitude towards mathematics field and field education lessons were at the same level. It was found that the attitude towards field and field education lessons did not show significant differences according to gender and class variables. Ay (2004) examined the benefits of primary and secondary school mathematics teachers and Primary School teacher candidates' field and vocational courses to their professional lives. As a result of the study, it was concluded that they have positive opinions about the field teaching lessons. Türker and Turanlı (2008) developed an attitude scale towards mathematics lessons in their research with prospective mathematics teachers.

When the literature is examined, it becomes clear that knowledge of mathematics education is important for mathematics teachers. Particularly for the elementary school level as for all other subjects, the importance of how to transfer the mathematical knowledge they have to the students is of great importance, since

there are years in which perceptions about concepts occur (Güveli, İpek, Atasoy and Güveli, 2011). For this reason, the research aimed to examine the students' attitudes at the Department of Primary School Teaching towards the mathematics education courses. The students' attitudes towards mathematics education courses will increase their ability to transfer mathematical knowledge and consequently the success of the students. In addition to this, it was aimed to investigate whether the students' attitude of the Department of Primary School Teaching towards mathematics courses vary according to the variables of class and parent education. For this purpose, the following questions were researched.

1. What are the attitudes of students of primary school teachers towards mathematics education lessons?
2. Do the attitudes of primary school teacher students in mathematics education lessons show a significant difference compared to the first and fourth grade students?
3. Do the attitudes of primary school teacher students in mathematics education lessons show a significant difference compared to the variable of the educational status of the parents?

2. Method

This study examines the attitudes of the students attending undergraduate education in the department of primary school teaching towards mathematics education lessons and it is a descriptive comparison study in general survey model.

Population and sample

The Population of the study consists of the students studying in the Department of Primary Education at the Faculty of Education of a state university. Since it is not possible to reach the population under the current conditions, a sample selection was made and purposeful sampling was taken from the students. Three of 168 students were not evaluated because they did not complete the questionnaire as requested and 165 students were the sample of the study.

Data collection tool

Attitude Scale for Mathematics Education lessons

Attitude Scale towards Mathematics Education lessons, developed by Türker and Turanlı (2008), was used to determine the attitudes of primary school students in mathematics education lessons. The scale is a five-point Likert-type scale with 18 items. The options of the items in the scale are given from “I fully agree” to “I Never agree”. The researchers found the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to be 0.928 for the reliability of the scale and factor analysis for validity indicated that the items of the scale were collected in one dimension. The reliability coefficient in this study was obtained as 0.883.

Analysis of data

SPSS 20.0 package program was used for data analysis. In order to examine the relationship between the attitudes of the elementary school students in mathematics education courses, descriptive values such as arithmetic mean, standard deviation and the normal distribution of data, the skewness, kurtosis coefficients and Kolmogorov-Smirnov values of mathematics education courses were calculated. The prerequisite for the independent group means significance tests is that the scale data should be interval or portion scale and have normal distribution (Büyüköztürk,

2010). When these prerequisites were examined, it was seen that the data were in the interval scale.

3. Findings

First Sub Problem

The first sub-problem of the study was given as “ What are the attitudes of students of primary school teachers towards mathematics education lessons?”. In order to answer this sub-problem, descriptive statistics were examined and “Table 1 shows the attitude score arithmetic mean and standard deviation values of the elementary school teachers' mathematics education lessons.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics related to attitude points towards mathematics education lessons

	Grade	n	X	SS
The attitude of the students	First grade	82	3,95	,320
	Forth grade	83	3,75	,252
	Total	165	3,85	,239

Total attitude towards mathematics education lessons mean score was 3.85, standard deviation, 239. As attitudes towards mathematics education lessons corresponded to 3.40-4.20, the attitudes of students towards mathematics education courses were good.

Second Sub Problem

The second sub-sentence of the study is “Do the attitudes of primary school teacher students in mathematics education lessons show a significant difference compared to the first and fourth grade students?” In order to test our hypothesis within the scope of the effects of the students' first and fourth grade on mathematics education

lessons, it is examined whether the data shows normal distribution and the findings are given in Table 2. According to the results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($p > .05$) it was decided that they show normal distribution.

Table 2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results

Grade	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
First grade	,094	79	,082	,944	79	,002
Forth grade	,076	80	,200*	,987	80	,621

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 3 shows the attitude score data of the students of the Department of Primary Teacher Education for mathematics education lessons according to the variability of the first and fourth grade students.

Table 3. According to the variable of being the first and fourth grade students' attitude score t test results

Variable	Grade	N	x	ss	df	T	p
The attitude of the students	First grade	82	3,95	,320	157	0,669	,504
	Forth grade	83	3,75	,252			

The independent sample t test was used to reveal whether the first or fourth grade students' attitudes towards mathematics education courses had a significant effect on the attitudes of primary school students. The first grade students' attitude score average ($x = 3.95$) was found. There was no significant difference between the attitude mean score of the fourth grade students ($x = 3.75$) in the Department of Primary School Teaching ($t = 0.669$, $p > 0.50$). In this case, it can be said that there

is no significant effect on the first and fourth grade students' attitudes towards mathematics education lessons of primary school students.

Third Sub Problem

The third sub-problem sentence of the study can be expressed as “Do the attitudes of primary school teacher students in mathematics education lessons show a significant difference compared to the variable of the educational status of the parents?” In order to test our hypothesis, attitude score data for mathematics education lessons of the elementary education teachers of the primary school teachers obtained from the Kruskal Wallis test, which is not normally distributed, is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Attitude scores of the students of the Department of Primary School Teaching towards mathematics education lessons according to the father of education level variable Kruskal Wallis test results

Variable	The father education level	N	Mean rank	df	Chi-square	P	Sig. tolerance
The attitude of the students	Literate	2	153,00	3	6,195	,102	-
	Primary education	63	79,59				
	Secondary education	46	89,24				
	Higher education	54	71,27				

When the average attitude scores of mathematics education lessons were compared according to the father education level of primary school students, fathers who were literate ($x = 153.00$) had the highest attitude score; this was followed by those whose fathers who had secondary education ($x = 89.24$), whose fathers had primary education ($x = 79.59$) and those whose fathers had higher education ($x = 71.27$).

These mean differences were found to be statistically insignificant at 0.05 significance level ($X = 1,377$, $p > 0.05$).

The attitude score data of the students of the Department of Primary School Teachers who obtained the Kruskal Wallis test with the data that do not show normal distribution according to the mother's educational status variable are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Attitude score of mathematics education students of primary school teachers according to mother education status variable Kruskal Wallis test results

Variable	The mother education level	N	Mean rank	fd	Chi-square	p	Sig. iferance
The attitude of the stu	Literate	9	97,94	3	1,377	,711	-
	Primary education	87	79,88				
	Secondary education	53	78,43				
	Higher education	16	76,21				

When the attitude scores of mathematics education courses of the primary school teachers were compared according to the mother's educational status variable, those whose mothers were literate ($x = 97.94$) had the highest attitude score; this was followed by mothers with primary education ($x = 79.88$), mothers with secondary education ($x = 78.43$) and mothers with higher education ($x = 76.21$). These mean differences were found to be statistically insignificant at 0.05 significance level ($X = 1,377$, $p > 0.05$).

When the attitude scores of mathematics education courses of the primary school teachers were compared according to their father-mother education status variable; it is worth examining that the literate father/mother children have the

highest attitude and the father-mother children who have higher education have the lowest attitude.

4. Discussion and conclusion

It was observed that the average score of total attitude towards mathematics education lessons grade was 3.85 for primary school students. It can be said that students' attitudes towards mathematics education lessons are at a good level. As a result of the studies of Özgen and Obay (2016), it was seen that the attitude scores of the prospective teachers towards mathematics field and the field of education were similar and positive. This study supports our study in terms of positive attitudes towards the application education lessons.

It has been determined that whether they are first or fourth grade students' attitudes towards mathematics education lessons has no significant effect on primary school students. This shows us that the mean attitude score of the students of Classroom Teaching Department does not change according to their grade levels. It can be said that the results obtained by Özgen and Obay (2016) in their researches showed that the attitude towards field education lessons did not show significant differences according to the grade variables.

When the attitude scores of mathematics education courses of the primary school teachers were compared according to the father-mother educational status variable; it is worth examining that the literate father/mother children have the highest attitude and the father/mother children who have higher education have the lowest attitude. One of the reasons for this result is that literate parents take care of the importance of education and support their children in order to be better.

5. Suggestions

Considering the importance of mathematics and especially the attitudes of students towards mathematics at primary level, which is the first years of this course, the enthusiasm and attitudes of the students of the Department of Primary School Teaching towards mathematics become very important because the attitude of the teacher will affect the students. At this point, it may be suggested that different studies will be conducted to reveal the importance of mathematics.

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